

ASSIMILATION OF BORROWED WORDS IN ENGLISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz tilidagi o'zlashtirilgan so'zlarning talqini va ularning tasnifi bilan bog'liq.

АННОТАЦИЯ. В данной статье речь идет о толковании заимствованных слов в английском языке и их классификации.

Annotation. This article deals with the interpretation of borrowed words in the English language and their classification.

Kalit so'zlar: *polisemantik so'zlar, paradigmalar, morfologik me'yorlar*, such a degree that the assimilating group becomes socially indistinguishable from other members of the society. As such, assimilation is the most extreme form of acculturation.

Assimilation is a process of adjusting in Phonetics and Lexicology. The term Assimilation in Etymology is used to denote a partial or total conformation of a borrowed word to the phonetical (graphical and morphological standards and the semantic system of the receiving language (язык-реципиент). There are three main types of Assimilation:

Phonetic Assimilation – the adjusting of the phonetic structure of a borrowed word to the phonetical system of the recipient language. Loan words not assimilated phonetically retain their foreign pronunciation like most of the French borrowings of the latest time, e.g. police, machine, ballet;

Grammatical Assimilation – a conformation of a borrowed word to the morphological standards of the receiving language. Grammatically assimilated loan words acquire English grammatical categories and paradigms, e.g. to count-counted-counting, sputnik-sputniks. Loan words not assimilated grammatically retain their foreign grammatical forms like some nouns borrowed from Latin which keep their original plural inflexions, e.g. phenomenon – phenomena.

Lexical Assimilation – a conformation of a borrowed word to the lexicosemantic system of the receiving language. It means that a borrowed word may participate in word building and develop its semantic structure, e.g. sputnik – to out sputniks, sputnikists. Foreign polysemantic words become monosemantic in the receiving language but a borrowed word may develop a new meaning in the receiving language, e.g. palate (the roof of the mouth) has developed a new

meaning in English = taste, inclination and interest; and the new derivatives – palatable (tasty).

Now our task is to see how our borrowings in English change and are subject to their specific characteristics. All types of borrowed items can be divided into two major groups. On the one hand, there are only changes specific to the word borrowed. These changes are aimed at adapting foreign words to the norms of the language of borrowing, e.g. the constant compounds [pn], [ps], [tpt] in the Greek words "pneumatics", "psychology", "ptolemy" are simplified to [n], [s], [t] because consonant compounds [ps], [pt], [pn] are very often used at the end of English words in the initial state. It is important to distinguish between the two processes: adapting the borrowed material to language norms and developing these words according to language laws. In many cases, we need to turn to historical analysis before we can draw clear conclusions. There is nothing in the form of the words "walk" and "progress," indicating that the former was used in England in the eleventh century, and the latter before the fifteenth century. The history of these words shows that the word *cortege*, along with other words in the English language, underwent a number of changes, including decline, accentuation, structure, change of sounds, and the word 'progress'. In the course of its historical development, borrowing has acquired new meanings that are sometimes not found in the previous semantic structure. As a rule, the development of new meanings takes place 50–100 years after the word is borrowed. The role of loan words in the formation and development of English vocabulary is dealt with in the history of the language. It is there that the historical circumstances are discussed under which words borrowed from Latin, from Scandinavian dialects, from Norman and Parisian, French and many other languages, including Russian, were introduced into English. Lexicology, on the other hand, has in this connection tasks of its own, being chiefly concerned with the material and the results of assimilation. The main problems of etymology and borrowed words as they concern the English language are comprehensively and consistently treated in Professor A.I. Smirnitkiy deals with these issues mainly in terms of word. Unassimilated words differ from assimilated words in their pronunciation, spelling, frequency, semantic structure and sphere of application. However, there is no distinct borderline between the two groups. So far no linguist has been able to suggest more or less comprehensive criteria for determining the degree of assimilation depends in the first place upon the time of borrowing. A classification of loan words according to the degree of assimilation can be only very general as no rigorous procedure for measuring it

has so far been developed. The following three groups may be suggested:

1. Completely assimilated borrowed words
2. Partially assimilated borrowed words
3. Unassimilated borrowed words or barbarism.

The group of partially assimilated words may be subdivided depending on the aspect that remains unaltered, i. e. according to whether the word retains features of spelling, pronunciation, morphology or denotation that are not English. The third group is not universally accepted, as it may be argued that words not changed at all cannot form part of the vocabulary of language, because they occur in speech only, but do not enter the language. Completely assimilated borrowed words are found in all the layers of older borrowings. They may belong to the first layer of Latin borrowings, e, g: cheese, street, wall, or wine. Among Scandinavian borrowed words we find such frequent nouns as husband, fellow, gate, root, wing; such verbs as call, die, take, want and adjectives like happy, ill, low, odd and wrong. Completely assimilated French words are extremely numerous and frequent. Suffice it to mention such everyday words as table, chair, face, figure, finish, matter. A considerable number of Latin words borrowed during the revival of learning are at present almost indistinguishable from the rest of the vocabulary. Neither animal nor article differ noticeable from native words. Uzbek language like English is vulnerable to new nations. It mainly enriches its word stock by loaning words from Persian, Arabic Russian and via Russian from European languages. A large number of words in Uzbek language are the words from Persian.

The second group containing partially assimilated borrowed words can be subdivided into subgroups. The oppositions are equipollent.

a) Loan words not assimilated semantically, because they denote objects and notions peculiar to the country from which they come. They may denote foreign clothing: mantilla, sombrero; foreign titles and professions: shah, rajah, sheik, bei, toreador; foreign vehicles: caique (Turkish), rickshaw (Chinese), food and drinks: pillow (Persian) sherbet (Arabian); foreign currency: krone (Denmark), rupee (India), zloty (Poland), peseta (Spain).

b) Borrowed words not assimilated grammatically, for example, nouns borrowed from Latin Greek which keep their original plural forms: bacillus; bacilli, crisis; crises, formula; formulae, index; indices. Some of these are also used in English plural forms, but in that case there may be a difference in lexical meaning as in: indices: indexes.

c) Loan words are not completely assimilated phonetically. The French words borrowed after 1650 afford good examples. Some of them emphasize the last syllable: car, cartoon, police.

d) Borrowed words are not grammatically fully mastered. This group, as V.I. Balinskaya shows are fairly large and varied. For example, there are words derived from French that do not say the last consonant, for example, battet, buffet, corpus. Some may retain a diacritical mark: cafe, cliché. In particular, French digraphs (ch, qu, ou) can be preserved in the spelling: bouquet, brioche. It is self-evident that these sets intersect, i.e., the word single and single credit often indicates incomplete assimilation in several respects at the same time. The third group of borrowings comprises the so-called barbarism, i. e. words from other languages used by English people in conversation or in writing but not assimilated in any way, and for which there are corresponding English equivalents.

In conclusion, English has gone through many periods of learning a large number of words from a particular language. These periods coincide with a period of great cultural exchanges between English speakers and speakers of other languages. Especially in times of strong cultural ties, debt waves are not sharply limited and can overlap. For example, the influence of the Norwegians on English began in the 8th century AD and continued very well after the Norman conquest brought a large amount of French into this French language. It is part of the cultural history of English speakers that they have always adopted loanwords from the languages of whatever cultures they have come in contact with. There have been few periods when borrowing became unfashionable, and there has never been a national academy in Britain, the U.S., or other English Speaking countries to attempt to restrict new loanwords, as there has been in many continental European countries. In this paragraph, attention should be paid to the assimilation of debt words as a method of interaction with the language system in general. The term assimilation of the borrowed words is used to denote partial or complete conformity to the phonetic, graphic, and morphological norms of the host language and its semantic system. The degree of assimilation depends on the duration of the period of its use in the language receiving the word, its frequency. Oral borrowings due to personal contacts are assimilated more completely and more rapidly than literary borrowings, borrowings through written speech. origin English word.

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